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LINEAR PARKS TO COMBAT CLIMATE CHANGE.

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Policy Statement

Climate change due to greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions from deforestation, transportation, energy consumption, waste generation, and disposal is the leading cause of extreme events affecting various regions worldwide. Part of the 2030 Agenda, SDG 13, deals with adopting urgent global measures to minimize or even end climate change. The Climate Action Plan has been adopted in several countries to identify and establish concrete priority measures for reducing GHG emissions, mitigation, and social, economic, environmental, and territorial adaptation. In the case of urban areas, several cities are seeking nature-based solutions. This is the case with the linear parks adopted to tackle problems arising from climate change, restoring vegetation around rivers and lakes, planting more trees in the streets, and forming and restoring forests.

Background

Scientists working on climate issues have shown that people are responsible for global warming over the last 200 years (UN: 2024). Since the 19th century, although natural changes have occurred due to variations in solar activity or significant volcanic eruptions, human activities have been the main driver of change, mainly due to burning fossil fuels such as coal, oil, and gas. As a result, we see temperature variations, heat islands, extreme drought events, water shortages, severe fires, rising sea levels, floods, catastrophic storms, landslides, melting poles, and decreased biodiversity.

The combating of climate change has become SDG 13 of the 2030 Agenda (UN: 2015), which targets actions to strengthen resilience and adaptive capacity to climate-related risks and natural disasters; integrate climate change measures into national policies, strategies, and planning; improve education, raise awareness and human and institutional capacity on climate change mitigation, adaptation, impact reduction, and early warning; promote mechanisms to build capacity for climate change-related planning and effective management (CNM: 2024). Also noteworthy is the implementation of the commitment made by developed countries, parties to the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC), to jointly mobilize US\$100 billion a year from 2020 to meet the needs of developing countries in the context of significant mitigation actions and transparency in implementation, and fully operationalizing the Green Climate Fund through its capitalization as soon as possible.

Central to this objective is the UN Convention as a guideline for countries' actions.

In this context, cities play an essential role, as they tend to have the highest GHG emissions caused by anthropogenic activities and where many impacts will occur. According to the World Cities 2022 report, the world's population will be 68% urban by 2050 (UN-Habitat:2022), and most of the construction will be concentrated in cities in Africa, Asia, and Latin America. According to the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC, 2019), 17 of the 50 countries most vulnerable to climate change are in Latin America, where the phenomenon is particularly acute.

Most cities need to be aware of the vulnerability of places and their populations and have efficient risk planning, management, and assessment systems (Marandola Jr., 2013, p. 12). The challenges are numerous, especially for the most vulnerable cities, which already suffer from densely populated informal urban settlements, many located in areas at risk of landslides and floods (Caldas et al., 2020). Climate change adds to pre-existing vulnerabilities, and extreme weather events already show that cities must prepare themselves to be more resilient. In addition to mitigating the climate crisis by accepting it as a reality, we must understand how to adapt. Coping with climate change involves mitigation, which is actions aimed at reducing GHG emissions, and adaptation, which is related to measures to adapt sectors of society, most of which are related to improving infrastructure and recovering degraded areas, such as creating green infrastructure and nature-based adaptation (Caldas et al., 2020).

Findings

As Nature-Based Solutions (NBS1)[1], linear parks, adopted to tackle problems arising from climate change, have the potential to rescue and preserve valley bottoms from inappropriate use, requalifying the space, allowing their use for reservoirs in areas subject to flooding and combining them with other NBS with increased vegetation, favoring biodiversity, increasing resilience to extreme events and climate mitigation (Gallardo Raimundo: 2023). The linear park can play a recuperative role in the degradation of water sources and become a physical barrier against irregular urban expansion. It helps preserve natural resources by providing permeable areas along the banks of water bodies and encouraging the reintroduction of native plant species into degraded areas. It also helps to stabilize and protect the banks, drain and clean the soil and water, provide a natural habitat for fauna, and minimize bank erosion, river silting, and flooding (BARRETO & DIEB, 2017). In addition, the aesthetic and landscape content of the linear park promotes the development of sports and leisure activities.

It provides a new connection with nature, generates new social behaviors, and evaluates the environment as an asset for all citizens to preserve.

In Brazil, some public policies have been approved to increase urban resilience, particularly the National Climate Change Policy (Federal Law 12.187/2009) and the National Civil Protection and Defense Policy (Federal Law 12.608/2012). Both indicate the creation of information and monitoring systems for urban disasters with coordinated action between the state and municipalities, a systemic and preventive approach to actions, planning based on research into risk areas in cities and increased participation by society. However, few instruments and actions have been implemented to change the conditions of the affected communities (Peres; Shenk: 2024).

The municipality of Porto Alegre was preparing to finalize its Climate Action Plan[2], which would prevent tragedies like the one that occurred in May (Filho: 2024). In addition to the capital, almost 95% of the cities in Rio Grande do Sul were affected by the heavy rains and consequent flooding. According to the Civil Defense report, the storms affected 471 Rio Grande do Sul's 497 cities- equivalent to 94.77%. In other words, only 26 cities had no rain-related impact (CNN Brazil: 2024).

Other Brazilian capitals such as São Paulo, Rio de Janeiro, Salvador, and Recife already have Climate Action Plans, as do significant global metropolises like Paris and New York. Some Brazilian municipalities such as Curitiba (whose Climate Change Adaptation and Mitigation Plan dates back to 2018) have been implementing actions such as Friends of the Rivers, 100,000 trees, the Water Reserve of the Future, and the future Inter 2 and electric BRT, which earned the capital of Parana the title of Smartest City in the World 2023 (Prefeitura, 2024).

Flood-prone cities such as Jaraguá do Sul, north of Santa Catarina, are betting on SbN by presenting the linear park as a practical measure. The Via Verde Linear Park, surrounded by a walking trail and equipped with sports courts, a gym, a skate park, and other leisure options, was developed and designed (inspired by similar spaces in New York and the Netherlands) to flood on purpose on days of heavy rain, acting as a temporary reservoir for river water. This system prevents floods from the Itapocu River, which runs through the city, from reaching streets and homes. The equipment installed is made of metal, plastic, or concrete and can be cleaned and reused as soon as the river recedes (Caroline, 2024).

The municipality of Conceição do Mato Dentro, in the state of Minas Gerais, impacted by large mining projects that put the region's water security in question (Becker: 2023), warns in its Master Plan of the need to establish mechanisms to promote land uses compatible with areas of interest for drainage, such as linear parks, recreation and leisure areas, community gardens and maintenance of native vegetation (Complementary Law: 2020).

In this sense, the CMD-CidadeCriativa proposal (Becker: 2017) has as its primary action to revitalize and transform the foundational streams of Vintém, Cuiabá, and Lava-pés, on whose banks the city was born, into a linear park and later into a tourist route. To this end, it proposes a socio-environmental diagnosis and a prognosis (action plan) involving the community around the watershed, especially young people, with environmental education activities. The Prainha Linear Park[3] is planned to be part of the Linear Parks Program as an SbN and climate change adaptation strategy for the municipality to revitalize watercourses, combining expansion and conservation of permeability, combating flooding, implement the fundamental sanitation law, creating a housing program to transfer people from risk areas to safe housing; creating leisure, sports, and the cultural regions.

In this process, instead of prioritizing the expansion of urban infrastructure and the promotion of roads that cater mainly to motor vehicles, prioritize the development of the green infrastructure component and alternative transport, avoiding the canalization and containment of streams or tributaries to make way for the expansion of road infrastructure. Civil Society Organizations (CSOs)[4] are developing several other actions with funds from a tax amendment from the Conceição do Mato Dentro legislature. These actions are helping to reclassify the streams' open areas, improve the local population's quality of life, encourage commerce, and make them attractive spots for visitors and tourists.

Considering the objectives of SDG 13 (UN: 2015), among others, these actions seek to strengthen resilience and adaptive capacity to climate-related risks and natural disasters; improve education, raise awareness and human and institutional capacity on climate change mitigation, adaptation, impact reduction, and early warning; promote mechanisms to build capacity for climate change-related planning and effective management. Accordingly, in 2024, the municipal government held a workshop entitled "Climate risk and feasibility analysis for Conceição do Mato Dentro" (Prefeitura CMD: 2024), following on from the Anglo-American mining company's Zero Carbon initiative

(ICLEI: 2021). However, the research for this policy brief reveals a need for more efficient coordination between local management and initiatives by CSOs, companies, universities, and other regional and international institutions to make complementary progress in tackling climate issues.

Recommendations

To tackle climate change at the local level, it is recommended to:

- Identify the most priority and vulnerable cities and areas for immediate action. Coastal cities, communities lacking basic infrastructure, and settlements located in risk areas tend to be the most vulnerable;
- Prioritize the most vulnerable population groups (children, women, the elderly, the malnourished, and people who are ill or immunocompromised) by including them in the process of designing and implementing linear park projects;
- Using technology to mitigate and adapt to climate change. Mitigation: implementing more efficient alternatives in various sectors (transport, energy, waste management, security, etc.) and accounting for inventories carried out in cities. Adaptation: increasing the speed and reliability of preventive measures and post-crisis response.
- Greater dissemination and implementation of nature-based solutions are essential strategies for both mitigation and adaptation in cities, and they should be prioritized mainly in the most vulnerable regions and cities (Caldas et Al., 2020).
- Promote awareness campaigns on climate change and involve the general population in drawing up the Climate Action Plan.

Conclusions

In the context of growing urbanization, green spaces take on not only environmental aspects but also social, economic, and cultural functions. They are strategies for climate change, preservation, and environmental recovery. The Climate Action Plan has been adopted in several countries because, in addition to identifying the consequences and risks that climate events can bring to regions, it presents measures to promote the adoption of renewable energies and the protection of natural areas and ecosystems. In the case of urban areas, one of the SbN is the linear park. Even if fragmented, urban forests can reduce air temperature, increase humidity, intercept solar radiation, and facilitate light winds close to the surface, making them local strategies for climate change. The historical, cultural, and natural value of some watercourses, such as the Córregos Fundacionais project in Conceição do Mato Dentro, listed as a historical, cultural, and natural heritage site (Municipal Law 2.475/2023), makes them even more strategic in the process. In this sense, public managers must take on a large part of the responsibility since there is an urgent need for a paradigm shift in how cities are designed and managed, promoting intelligent and participatory planning with a focus on improving the quality of life of its citizens.

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[1] A term coined by the European Union that includes engineering solutions that mimic natural processes and aim to simultaneously meet environmental, social, and economic objectives. NBS is based on seven principles: delivering an effective solution to a global challenge using nature; providing biodiversity benefits in terms of diversity and well-managed ecosystems; presenting the best cost-effectiveness ratio when compared to other solutions; being communicated and convincingly; being able to be measured, verified and replicated; respecting and reinforcing the rights of communities over natural resources; linking public and private funding sources. (Ecycle: Understand what Nature-Based Solutions are and why it is essential to apply them. Available at <https://www.ecycle.com.br/solucoes-baseadas-na-natureza/>. Access on 4/jun/2024.

[2] This document brings together a set of strategies cities should adopt to tackle climate change. It aims to identify and establish concrete priority measures for reducing GHG emissions, mitigation, and social, economic, environmental, and territorial adaptation.

[3] The name Prainha was suggested to preserve the sandy characteristics of the stream, which, before the urban sprawl near its banks, formed small white sand beaches used as a leisure area by the families who lived there and passers-by.

[4] For example, the projects of the Mato Dentro Association. Among others, regarding the urban streams that cross the municipality's headquarters, we can mention the Community Library project with a collection linked to environmental and heritage education; the Córregos Fundacionais project that seeks to integrate environmental education into the curriculum of municipal schools under the skills of the National Common Curriculum Base – BNCC; the Agroecological Productive Backyards project, which seeks to promote community social mobilization actions with a focus on implementing productive backyards around the micro-basin of the foundational streams of Conceição do Mato Dentro, by offering training activities, experiences and reflections on principles and concepts related to Agroecology, Water Resources, and Syntropic or Regenerative Agriculture. Available at <https://matodentro.org.br/projetos/>. Access 2/jun/2024>.

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